

Rapid decline in the uptake interests for different SARS CoV-2 vaccination doses over the post vaccination period in different European community countries

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Abstract:

Aim: During the corona virus pandemic outbreak, there are a number of vaccinations approved. They are distributed and used in human beings worldwide. Aim of this study is to analyze the changes in pattern of uptake mood during different dose courses in EU /EEA population.

Methods: The data from official European community website was collected and analyzed with the software for total number of doses distributed and total number of doses applied. Similarly, cumulative percentage of uptake of vaccine from primary course, first booster, second booster and third booster were compared.

Results. They are showing that there is difference of around 0.5 billion doses between the doses distributed and doses used. The uptake interest decreased from primary dose to third booster dose from 85% to 0% among the countries over the time.

Conclusion: There are discrepancies between the total number of doses distributed and used. There is very strong loss of uptake interest in the populations in EU/EEA with different dose courses. One must study the reasons for such a strong loss of uptake interest and economic losses caused leading to burden on the tax payers.

Keywords: Vaccine effectiveness, Uptake, SARS CoV-2, Booster dose

Introduction: The vaccine is thought to be one key strategy to create immunity among the populations. Vaccines have been very success to reduce the cases of several viral diseases like HBV, Rubella, Measles, Mumps, Polio etc. Even viruses like small pox has been eradicated fully. (1, 2, 3) Now there are other types of viruses like influenza strains, which change their structures continuously leading to the reinfections among the people. SARS CoV-2 is a new virus, which caused infections from the beginning from January 2020 till today. (3,4) The vaccines against this virus were thought to reduce the cases of infections, therefore a number of different vaccines were developed and used worldwide. The mutations in this virus are still causing several outbreaks in many countries in the world. (5)

In the literature, there are a number of research groups, which have made studies about the vaccine effectiveness. All groups are pointing out that the vaccine effectiveness is very short lived, and it drops very strongly within a very short period, therefore 4 different doses at different interval of period were used to vaccinate the populations in EU/EEA. (5,6,7,8) It is also found that there is reoccurrence of infections in vaccinated populations along with vaccines cause themselves complications. The data about the vaccinations are available online. A group has studied the vaccine effectiveness in cancer patients. (9) Another group has studied the uptake mood in Omicron booster dose in USA. (10) The Strategies to boost the vaccines has been discussed in countries like South Africa. (11) Other studies about the pattern of mortalities in vaccinated persons were published and discussed. (12)

In this study, we decided to analyze the data about vaccinated population to find whether this is any change in the pattern of uptake mood during the post vaccination period starting from the primary course to 3rd booster dose in different countries in EU/EEA

Method: The data about total vaccine doses distributed, total number of vaccinated doses, total number of vaccinated with different doses and cumulative percentages of different doses were taken from the European community website: [COVID-19 Vaccine Tracker | European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control \(europa.eu\)](https://ecdc.europa.eu/en/covid-19/vaccine-tracker) and this data was processed according to different criteria to calculate the different patterns for various behaviors among the different countries. Variations between the cumulative percentage of different countries were compared for primary course, first booster, second booster and third booster to order to show the change in uptake mood of populations from EU/EEA. (13) The graphics about change in uptake mood were generated with Microsoft office software.

Results: The data from EU/EEA shows that total number of 1 481 436 092 doses were distributed till today and 981 218 341 doses were used. These were primary course, first booster, second booster and 3rd booster. Total number of doses according to persons vaccinated with different doses were 645,471,432 (primary course 330,677,385, first Booster 248,150,311, second booster 66, 643,736) as exact numbers are shown in table 1. Cumulative vaccine uptake is showing that the percentage of persons were highest with the primary course and it is lowest with 3rd dose as the percentage varies between 73% with primary course to 2.4% with third dose.

Cumulative percentage of uptake for primary course varies between different countries: 30% in Bulgaria to 86.1% (Netherland) and cumulative percentage of uptake of first booster (second dose) dropped strongly in all countries in EU/EEA ranging between 9.2% in Romania to 76% in Italy. Uptake interest for 2nd booster (third dose) dropped further for all vaccinated persons as they were 0.2% in Romania to 30% in Portugal as well as Poland. It is found that uptake interest dropped in eastern countries strongly and it was less than 1%. 3rd booster dose (4th dose) shows strongly dropped interest against that of primary course as it was almost 0% in many eastern European countries like Romania, Bulgaria, Croatian etc. to 12.6% in Portugal. The data shows that there is continuous loss of uptake interest starting from primary course to third booster dose.

Results shows that there is difference of almost 500 million doses between distributed doses and administered doses. Further analysis shows that there were 644 million persons were vaccinated, but website is showing all most 1 billion doses were administered, it shows a gap of around 300 million.

Discussion: It is shown in this research that there is rapid loss of uptake interest for the coronavirus vaccination during a very short period around 2 years, but there are preparations going to deploy the 4th booster dose (5th dose) and people are lost interest with so many vaccinations as there are so many studies, which indicate that there is a reduction in immunity provided through these vaccinations as well as there are a number of complications, not only this, a number of people got the breakthrough infections single as well as multiple times. (5,6,7,8) Such a loss of interest in vaccination may be serious problem as this can impact the uptake of other important vaccines, which provide good immunity for long term. There is an urgent need to develop a new and better vaccine as the present vaccines are not enough to convince the people and communications methods are not functioning any more to convince all people to get another shot of vaccination. Moreover, there are publications, which indicate that breakthrough infections can improve the immunity as the body generates the response against other part of coronaviruses, where as the vaccines are only against S proteins. (14)

There are many questions about the number of doses. There is difference of 500 million doses between distributed and administered. What happened to these 500 million doses. As only 664 persons got the doses, there is another difference of 340 million doses. There is total difference of all most 800 million doses, where they have gone. This may indicate that there may be some misuse! According to German press, 10 billion doses are ordered, and 35 billion Euro was paid. The data shows that 1.5 billion doses are used till now. It means that 8.5 billion doses are still to be delivered. The question is now there is reduction in uptake interest in the vaccines. It indicates that there is huge waste of money. It opens a question what is the sense of 4th booster, if there is such a rapid loss in vaccine uptake. (15)

Conclusion: The studies indicate that there is a strong decline in the uptake mood of the populations of different EU/EEA countries over the different vaccine courses. There is an urgent need to work the reasons for such strong decline and financial burden caused on tax payers.

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Table 1

Table 1: shows total number of vaccine distributed, vaccines used and number of persons vaccinated with 3 different doses.

Table 2: shows maximum and minimum of cumulative percentages of different dose courses for SARS CoV-2 vaccines in EU/EEA countries.